

E2.2 Report on requirements for AI Pipelines in the edge to cloud continuum

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List of Acronyms

IA	Artificial Intelligence
5G/6G	Fifth/sixth generation wireless networks
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
DL	Distributed Learning
FL	Federated Learning
ML	Machine Learning
MARL	Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Delivery

Table 1 List of Acronyms

Executive Summary

The report for the project "6GENABLERS, IA for 6G: Ultra Automation and Optimization," reference number TSI-063000-2021-10, addresses two main objectives in its task A2.2. The first is Applied Research, focusing on defining specific use cases for automating 5G/6G networks using Artificial Intelligence technologies. This research aims to identify efficient and effective ways to integrate AI into these advanced networks. The second objective is Architecture Design, aimed at developing a scalable and reliable architecture to implement the identified use cases. This involves creating a framework that facilitates the integration of AI into the network, adapting to future needs.

The document presents an extensive and detailed literature review of distributed learning (DL) and federated learning (FL), providing a critical evaluation of their advantages and disadvantages across various use case scenarios. This thorough bibliographic study illuminates the latest advancements and persistent needs within the realm of 5G networks. By offering an in-depth understanding of these cutting-edge learning methodologies, the study not only captures the current technological landscape but also aligns the project's goals with the leading edge of the industry. This approach ensures that the project's strategies and solutions are informed by the most recent and relevant developments in the field, positioning it at the forefront of 5G network innovation.

Additionally, the document delves deeply into the system requirements critical for implementing AI process chains, emphasizing the seamless Integration of AI from Edge Computing to Cloud. This section meticulously identifies both functional and system-level requirements necessary for the native integration of AI processes, an essential step for the effective incorporation of AI-enabled network operations.

Furthermore, the document conducts an in-depth analysis of various AI Methods and Control Loops. This examination is crucial in ensuring that the diverse range of AI strategies and mechanisms are effectively harmonized within the network's ecosystem.

Lastly, a significant focus is placed on the Identification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Thresholds. This part of the document is dedicated to establishing clear benchmarks and performance standards necessary to guarantee optimal functionality and efficiency across all segments of the network. These KPIs and thresholds are pivotal in measuring the success and effectiveness of the AI integration within the network infrastructure.

1 Introduction

In the rapidly evolving world of telecommunications, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) into network operations has become imperative, especially with the advent of 6G networks. These networks, known for their unprecedented speed and capabilities, present a unique opportunity to revolutionize how we manage and optimize networks. Central to harnessing this potential is addressing the critical challenges in Machine Learning Operations (MLOps), particularly within the context of network slicing.

The concept of distributed MLOps emerges as a key solution in this scenario. Unlike traditional MLOps, which may operate in a more centralized manner, distributed MLOps in the realm of 6G networks involves a seamless and modular integration of AI/ML across the network's various segments. This approach is crucial in aligning with the distributed nature of network slicing, where different slices of the network can have tailored AI solutions that operate independently yet cohesively.

A significant advancement in this area is the development of a dedicated MLOps plane, analogous to the separation between the user plane (UP) and control plane (CP) in network architectures. This plane, functioning as a distributed cross-domain slice, is responsible for managing the lifecycle of AI models and delivering them as artifacts tailored to the specific technological domain of each network slice.

The implementation of this distributed MLOps architecture is further facilitated by various open-source platforms such as Kubeflow and MLflow. These platforms simplify the management of all stages of the ML lifecycle, making the process more straightforward, reliable, and efficient. They are instrumental in handling the complexities of deploying, monitoring, and maintaining ML models in a distributed network environment.

In the pages that follow, we delve deeper into the concept of distributed MLOps, exploring its benefits, implementation strategies, and its pivotal role in ushering in the era of AI-driven 6G networks. It represents a paradigm shift in the way we approach network management, ensuring that AI and ML are seamlessly woven into the fabric of future-proof telecommunications.

2 Bibliography Study

In this section, review the literature of distributed learning (DL) and federated learning (FL) evaluating their pros and cons in different use case scenarios.

2.1 State-of-the-Art Review

In their work¹, the authors address the application of FL techniques within the context of emerging sixth generation (6G) wireless networks. Unlike conventional machine learning methods that centralize data for training in a data centre, FL allows devices to train a shared machine learning model without the need to transmit data, providing a viable solution in the face of privacy restrictions and limited communication resources. Throughout the document, FL applications in wireless communications are thoroughly explored, identifying their essential requirements, potential applications, and the predominant challenges associated with such implementations, culminating in a discussion about a comprehensive implementation of FL for wireless communications.

In this second work², The authors provide a thorough analysis concerning the anticipated increase in popularity of smart services based on the Internet of Things (IoT) and the subsequent need to enhance and upgrade fifth generation (5G) cellular networks. The paper underscores the limitations of 5G networks in fully meeting the requirements of emerging smart applications, exploring the development of sixth generation (6G) wireless technologies as a solution that addresses these shortfalls. Emphasis is placed on DL techniques, such as FL and Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL), discussing how these approaches can be effectively and efficiently deployed in wireless networks. Moreover, the article provides a detailed review of the role of FL in facilitating 6G enabling technologies, identifies and discusses open research issues related to FL-powered 6G wireless networks, and ultimately outlines various perspectives on upcoming research topics, focused on the constructive incorporation of the MARL-based FL framework for future wireless networks.

Finally in work³, the authors explore the projection and implementation of 6G communication networks, with a special focus on the integration and utility of federated learning in the environment of these future networks. The authors argue that 6G will be fundamentally grounded in ubiquitous Artificial Intelligence (AI), aimed at generating data-driven Machine Learning (ML) solutions in heterogeneous and massive-scale networks. It is emphasized that while conventional ML techniques require centralized data collection and processing, this approach is encountering obstacles, particularly in terms of privacy concerns. In this context, federated learning emerges as a privacy-preserving distributed AI strategy, positioning itself as particularly attractive for various wireless applications and being regarded as essential for achieving ubiquitous AI in 6G. The article's discussion extends over the integration of 6G and federated learning, also

1 Zhaohui Yang, Mingzhe Chen, Kai-Kit Wong, H. Vincent Poor, Shuguang Cui, in "Federated Learning for 6G: Applications, Challenges, and Opportunities" January 2022 Research 6G Requirements, Vision, and Enabling Technologies—Review ELSEVIER

2 Das, Sree Krishna; Mudi, Ratna; Rahman, Md. Siddikur; Fapojuwo, Abraham O. (2022): Distributed Learning for 6G–IoT Networks: A Comprehensive Survey. TechRxiv. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.20069051.v3>

3 Yi Liu, Xingliang Yuan, Member, IEEE, Zehui Xiong, Jiawen Kang, Xiaofei Wang, Senior Member, IEEE, Dusit Niyato, Fellow, IEEE, in "Federated Learning for 6G Communications: Challenges, Methods, and Future Directions" arXiv:2006.02931v2 [cs.NI] 12 Jul 2020

providing insight into potential applications, technical challenges, and open fields for future research at the intersection of federated learning and 6G communications.

2.2 Comparative review and Analysis

This section provides a comparative review and analysis of works on Federated Learning and 6G.

W	Discussion	Methodology	Challenges	Contributions
1	The focus is on applying FL as a viable strategy to address privacy restrictions and limited communication resources.	Through a thorough exploration, the author identifies essential requirements, potential applications, and challenges of FL in wireless communications.	It is highlighted that the main challenges associated with implementing FL in wireless networks stem from privacy restrictions and communication resources.	The primary contribution is a discussion on the comprehensive implementation of FL for wireless communications, based on the theoretical and practical exploration of its applications and requirements.
2	The discussion explores the development of 6G wireless technologies as a solution to meet the requirements of emerging intelligent applications based on IoT.	The methodology seems to focus on analysing and discussing how DL techniques, like FL and MARL, can be effectively and efficiently deployed in wireless networks.	The paper identifies and discusses open research issues related to FL-powered 6G wireless networks.	Provides a detailed review of the role of FL in facilitating 6G enabling technologies and sketches perspectives on upcoming research topics, focusing on the constructive incorporation of the MARL-based FL framework.
3	It extends over the integration of 6G and FL, grounding that 6G will be deeply rooted in AI, aimed at generating data-driven ML solutions in large-scale, heterogeneous networks.	Not clearly specified, but the discussion seems to be based on the theoretical projection and exploration of how ubiquitous AI can be achieved through FL in 6G networks.	Identifies obstacles, particularly in terms of privacy concerns, with conventional ML techniques requiring centralized data collection and processing.	The paper not only highlights applications and technical challenges of integrating FL into 6G but also provides insight into open fields for future research at the intersection of FL and 6G communications.

Table 2 Comparative Review of Previous Works on Federated Learning and 6G

All three works emphasize the importance and potential of FL in the context of 6G networks. All discuss the limitations of traditional ML techniques and see FL as a viable solution to overcome challenges related to privacy and data centralization. Emphasize the need to advance from current 5G networks to meet the demands of emerging and massive intelligent applications. Differences:

Work 1 directly focuses on the aspect of applications and requirements of FL in the 6G environment. Work 2 presents a robust analysis of how DL techniques, especially FL and MARL, can be effectively deployed in wireless networks and discusses their applications in enabling 6G technologies. Work 3 provides a detailed exploration of how the integration of FL and 6G might occur and discusses technical challenges and future areas of research at the confluence of FL and 6G. Each work, while exploring the same

thematic domain of 6G and Federated Learning, brings unique perspectives and approaches, resulting in complementary contributions to the field of study.

2.3 Federated Learning vs Distributed Learning

While it might be tempting to consider Federated Learning as an "improvement" over Distributed Learning, it's essential to recognize that they address slightly different problems and scenarios. FL is not strictly superior to DL; rather, it offers an alternative approach that emphasizes privacy and utilizes data in its local environment to avoid transmission to a central server. This does not necessarily make it "better", but rather makes it more suitable for certain use cases, particularly where privacy and data locality are paramount.

#	Aspect	Distributed Learning	Federated Learning
1	Use Case and Application Relevance	Often used where data transmission to various nodes is permissible or desired and needs to handle large-scale data.	Suited for scenarios where data transmission is not viable due to privacy, legal, or bandwidth issues and emphasizes on-device computations.
2	Data Centralization and Transmission	Involves partitioning and potentially centralizing data, distributing it across different nodes for processing.	Data remains localized on devices (e.g., smartphones), and only model updates are communicated to the central server, not the raw data.
3	Privacy and Security Considerations	Privacy may or may not be a priority, depending on the application and setup. It might involve transmitting sensitive data between nodes.	Prioritizes privacy by keeping raw data localized and may apply differential privacy and secure aggregation methods to maintain data security and privacy during model update transmissions.
4	Model Training and Update Strategy	Updates (e.g., gradients or model parameters) from nodes are commonly combined in a straightforward manner, like averaging.	Involves sophisticated and potentially secure aggregation methods to amalgamate model updates from devices in a privacy-preserving manner, considering the disparate, decentralized data sources.
5	Computational Complexity and Resource Use	Can be computationally intensive due to processing large datasets and requires communication between nodes to synchronize updates.	May be computationally lighter on the central server since it leverages edge devices for local computations. Yet, it demands efficient algorithms to handle myriad model updates from numerous devices.
6	Network and Communication	Requires robust, and potentially high-bandwidth, communication to handle data or extensive model parameter transmissions between nodes.	May work efficiently with lower bandwidth since it mainly involves transmitting essential model updates, which might be less data-intensive than transmitting extensive data or model parameters.

Table 3 Distributed vs Federation Learning Aspects

Federated Learning (FL) and Distributed Learning (DL) provide robust solutions for managing large-scale data, each with their own challenges and strengths. While FL offers advantages in privacy preservation by keeping data on local devices, it faces obstacles such as "stragglers" and non-IID data distributions. On the other hand, DL

excels in processing large data sets across distributed nodes but requires detailed considerations regarding data transmission and privacy.

3 Architecture

The architecture is organized into modular components and is offered as a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) solution, encompassing interface components or connectors that facilitate access across various edge-to-cloud tiers. The service or function layer executes these modules and is segmented by layer, bestowing upon this level the requisite abstraction capability over the data that needs to be processed by the remaining functionalities of the platform.

Subsequent sections provide an overview and delineate best practices, starting with the foundational General MLOps framework, and progressing towards adapting it to a distributed MLOps Architecture suitable for 6G Networks.

3.1 General MLOps Framework

Cloud Google suggests following MLOps architecture⁴, illustrating an implementation of the ML pipeline using CI/CD. This architecture incorporates the features of an automated ML pipeline setup, enriched with automated CI/CD routines.

Figure 1 automated AI pipelines general architecture

⁴ <https://cloud.google.com/architecture/mlops-continuous-delivery-and-automation-pipelines-in-machine-learning?hl=es-419>

This architecture includes the following components:

- **Source control:** Versioning the Code, Data, and ML Model artifacts.
- **Test and build services:** Using CI tools for (1) Quality assurance for all ML artifacts, and (2) Building packages and executables for pipelines.
- **Deployment services:** Using CD tools for deploying pipelines to the target environment.
- **Model registry:** A registry for storing already trained ML models.
- **Feature store:** Preprocessing input data as features to be consumed in the model training pipeline and during the model serving.
- **ML metadata store:** Tracking metadata of model training, for example model name, parameters, training data, test data, and metric results.
- **ML pipeline orchestrator:** Automating the steps of the ML experiments.

3.1.1 Workflow

The following diagram shows the stages of the ML automation pipeline:

Figure 2 automated AI pipelines workflow

The pipeline consists of the following stages:

Development and experimentation: You iteratively try out new ML algorithms and new modelling where the experiment steps are orchestrated. The output of this stage is the source code of the ML pipeline steps that are then pushed to a source repository.

Pipeline continuous integration: You build source code and run various tests. The outputs of this stage are pipeline components (packages, executables, and artifacts) to be deployed in a later stage.

Pipeline continuous delivery: You deploy the artifacts produced by the CI stage to the target environment. The output of this stage is a deployed pipeline with the new implementation of the model.

Automated triggering: The pipeline is automatically executed in production based on a schedule or in response to a trigger. The output of this stage is a trained model that is pushed to the model registry.

Model continuous delivery: You serve the trained model as a prediction service for the predictions. The output of this stage is a deployed model prediction service.

Monitoring: You collect statistics on the model performance based on live data. The output of this stage is a trigger to execute the pipeline or to execute a new experiment cycle.

3.2 Distributed MLOps Architecture suitable for 6G Networks

The foundation of MLOps, particularly in the context of 6G AI-native networks, is significantly strengthened by emphasizing the principles of distributed learning. This approach is key to standardizing production methods by integrating Continuous Integration (CI) and Continuous Delivery (CD) to enable the rapid and reliable development of software and AI solutions.

In a 6G environment, where AI-native networks are paramount, the modular design of MLOps becomes crucial. It allows for the development, enhancement, and scaling of MLOps layers and AI functionalities independently from the service layers. This modular approach is especially beneficial in distributed learning scenarios, where AI models are trained across various nodes in the network, optimizing resource usage and enhancing performance.

Figure 3 illustrates an example of operational AI-native slice at the top of the network slicing environment, showcasing three specific instances: URLLC, eMBB, and met. Each instance provides specialized AI services to its corresponding network segment. These instances can efficiently collaborate, particularly in **distributed learning contexts**, for tasks such as resource allocation, where resources are shared among various service slices.

A key advantage of distributed learning in MLOps is its ability to maintain AI performance isolation. This is achieved through re-training triggers, ensuring that any performance degradation in one slice instance minimally affects others. This aspect is crucial in distributed learning environments, where different nodes may have varying performance and capacity. The use of containerized solutions further supports this, decoupling the execution of iterative processes, a necessity in Machine Learning pipelines, particularly in distributed learning setups.

By adhering to these principles, MLOps in a 6G AI-native network effectively leverages distributed learning to enhance the overall efficiency and scalability of AI applications, ensuring they are robust, adaptable, and capable of meeting the dynamic demands of modern network infrastructures, as reflected in the URLLC, eMBB, and mMTC slices.

Figure 3 Distributed automated AI pipelines in the edge to cloud continuum.

High Precision Telemetry Data (1): It is considered as a backbone step in ML practices where data acquisition is utilized for data preparation and model design processes. It allows telemetry agents that run as containers instances within different domines to collect real-time monitoring key performance indicators (KPIs), encompassing available resources, number of connected devices, bandwidth utilization, channel quality, etc. This component can store structured and unstructured data on a very large scale.

Machine Learning Steps (2): It corresponds to the basic level of maturity, where all the ML steps, including data collection and preparation, model training, and validation, are performed manually. Hence, it is called no MLOps. At this level, data scientists usually use a rapid application development tool to build learning models, such as Jupiter Notebooks. Note that the transitions from one step to another are also performed manually, and driven by a source code, developed interactively, till an executable model is created System Requirements.

Training Pipeline Automation (3): This level introduces a continuous training of the models and thus consists of to perform the model training steps automatically. When new data profiles are monitored, the model retraining process is triggered. This process also includes data and model validation phases to achieve continuous delivery of the learning models. This level introduces two new components, named feature store as a centralized repository to store features and enable access to new features for training serving, and machine learning metadata to store information about the execution of ML pipeline.

Model Training, Evaluation and Saving (4, 5, 6): This module is segregated into a set of processes for the execution of continuous model training automatically with processed data. The ML model training runs a local optimization task, while the model explanation involves an explainer, either attribution-based (e.g., Integrated Gradient, Saliency Maps) or perturbation-based (e.g., SHAP13). Upon the evaluation of RL reward including interpretability metric, the model retraining is triggered whenever there is a model performance deterioration following new training data arrival (new unexplored states). Note that the reward should also correlate with slice targets (SLA, KPIs, etc.), while the interpretability refers to XAI metrics (attributions-based entropy, confidence, log-odds, fidelity, etc.) depending on the SLA adopted by the slice tenant. In this respect, a feedback loop between the explainer and the model is necessary to feed the model optimizer with the measured XAI metrics, enabling thereby explain ability-aware learning. Finally, in case the model fulfils the target performance, it will be registered and stored in the model registry to be promoted into production later.

Continuous Integration and Delivery Pipeline Automation (7): At this level, a complete CI/CD system is introduced, to enable reliable and fast learning model deployments in production. Thus, this level achieves the highest level of automation in ML Ops, by enabling data scientists and developers to efficiently explore new ideas about feature engineering, model hyperparameters, and architecture. The main difference with the last level is that this level enables to build, validate, and automatically deploy the data, learning models, and model training pipeline components. Fig. 3 shows the automation of the ML pipeline using CI/CD in slices context, which mainly features automated both ML pipelines and CI/CD routines.

AI Service Provisioning (8): The next step after training and evaluation is to retrieve the registered model for encapsulation and move to the production stage in the form of a model prediction service. The trained model is continuously exposed and delivered as representational state transfer (REST) application programming interface (API).

3.2.1 Workflow – Anomaly detection uses case.

The diagram below illustrates the stages of the machine learning automation pipeline tailored for anomaly detection uses case.

Figure 4 workflow of anomaly detection uses case.

Data Processing and Model Training: Public cloud⁵ services streamline critical stages within the framework, including continuous delivery, deployment, and monitoring on edge devices, as well as orchestrating cloud-to-edge communications.

Model Selection: The chosen models are containerized and deployed to the designated edge devices. Each model exists as a container image, created by the MLOps pipeline. Upon platform initialization, the edge controller retrieves the Data streaming. Subsequently, it regularly queries the container registry to determine the availability of updated model versions, downloading them as necessary.

Inference: The model consists of the inference API (more detail in 3.2.2), which takes data from the edge controller, transforms them, feeds them into the model for inference, and produces an output. Once an inference result is obtained, the edge controller performs two actions.

- First, it will store the sensor data, inference results, and device internal data in the data store. This data can be accessed by the performance monitor through an HTTP REST API server to analyse performance degradation.
- Analysis results can be sent to an external application, which may decide if the MLOps pipeline needs to be triggered to re-train the model.

⁵ <https://aws.amazon.com/es/solutions/implementations/mlops-workload-orchestrator>
<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/architecture/ai-ml/guide/mlops-python>
<https://www.databricks.com/blog/2022/06/22/architecting-mlops-on-the-lakehouse.html>

Analytics as Actions: The predicted anomalies are reported to high precision telemetry system which raises an alarm notifying or action.

3.2.2 Inference API flow

In crafting a platform for connecting edge devices to MLOps pipelines, essential tools and services are required to build and integrate edge infrastructure with these pipelines. A core feature of the platform is the automated AI pipelines in the cloud layer, as shown in Figure 3, with a Continuous Integration (CI) pipeline that trains ML models and packages them into Docker containers with an Inference API, allowing edge devices to perform model inferences.

Figure 5 Inference API Flow

The purpose of the **Inference API** is to establish the file structure of the inference API depicted in Figure 5, streamlining the model packaging process to ensure compatibility with inference execution on edge devices. It offers a template for the inference process, guiding users through the steps (model loading, preprocessing, inference, and output) and enabling them to implement the code needed to utilize the packaged ML model for running inferences on incoming data. This is provided in the Python programming language. The following Python functions must be implemented by the user, with the arguments denoting the necessary resources for each step of inference:

- **load_model (models_dir, model_name):** This function loads a model by retrieving the packaged model file and storing it in memory as an object of the trained model.

- **preprocess_input (input_data, models_dir):** This handles the structured input in any format and restructures it to be compatible with the model.
- **infer (model, input_data):** This function runs the inference on the restructured input data.
- **output (inference_result):** This converts the inference results into a format suitable for analysis (e.g., JSON).

Once the packaged model is deployed on an edge device, the executor takes over the inference process. It starts by subscribing to the input topic to receive sensor data. It then executes the load model function and keeps the model object in memory to avoid fetching the model with each sensor input received. Following this, it processes the input, runs the inference, and executes the output functions in sequence, forwarding the inference results to the edge controller.

In addition to the Inference Handler, the tool generates a **manifest** and **Dockerfile**. The manifest file's purpose is to adopt a declarative abstraction approach. It is a JSON file that details the model and the requirements for running an inference, including:

- The model's name.
- Version
- The directory and file name of the model
- The message topic to expect input from
- The message topic to send the inference results to

3.3 Tools to implement MLOps Architecture

This section provides background insights regarding the tools available to support MLOps, which will be explored in this project as potential solutions for implementing the proposed architecture. Please, note that this section doesn't aim to encompass all available tools, but rather to provide an overview of the most popular tools in both open-source and public cloud domains.

To this end, we have structured this section into two subsections. Subsection 3.3.1 offers a comprehensive market overview of the most popular MLOps tools currently available. While Subsection 3.3.2 proposes a concrete selection of MLOps tools, serving as potential candidates for project needs.

3.3.1 End-to-End MLOps Tools Map

MLOps tools have been grouped into four categories based on their main functionality within the MLOps lifecycle.

Figure 6 Tools and subcategories to produce MLOps Pipelines⁶

Plan:

- Data Management: Selection of tools for organizing and preparing data for ML training.
- Pipeline Design: Tools for constructing pipelines, including dependency management, workflow orchestration, and visualization features.

Build:

- Version Control: Systems to track and control changes to the codebase.

Test:

- Code Testing: Tools focused on validating code integrity.
- ML Model Testing: Systems for assessing ML models and their training datasets.

Release/Deploy:

- Configuration Management: Solutions for maintaining product attribute consistency.
- Deployment and Serving: Automation tools for deploying ML models and integrating them into existing systems.
- Infrastructure Provisioning: Tools for setting up the necessary infrastructure resources.

Operate:

- Containers: Technologies for packaging code and dependencies for consistent deployment across environments.
- Orchestration: Systems for managing container lifecycles, scheduling, and maintenance tasks.

⁶ Toward End-to-End MLOps Tools Map: A Preliminary Study based on a Multivocal Literature Review, arXiv:2304.03254v1 [cs.SE] 6 Apr 2023

Monitor:

- Application Performance: Tools for scrutinizing application metrics.
- Event Management: Systems for event monitoring and alerts.
- Infrastructure Surveillance: Tools for overseeing infrastructure components.
- ML Lifecycle Management: Tools for tracking experiments, managing datasets, and model lifecycle.
- Production Model Oversight: Systems to monitor live ML models to prevent performance degradation or failures.

3.3.2 MLOps Candidate Tools

In the creation of a comprehensive MLOps platform, initiating the process with a well-thought-out design for the framework or architecture, tailored to specific requirements, is highly advisable. This initial step should involve gathering insights from all pertinent teams, as the success of MLOps solutions is deeply rooted in robust and effective communication across various teams.

The architecture of such a platform typically unfolds in two distinct but interconnected phases, each characterized by its unique yet interrelated processes. These phases are Continuous Integration (CI) and Continuous Delivery (CD). In this context, teams employ a CI/CD pipeline as a strategic approach to ensure the seamless development and consistent delivery of models, maintaining a steady flow of updates and improvements.

Below, we have identified and listed the candidate tools that are optimally suited for the development of this end-to-end (E2E) MLOps architecture:

Figure 7 MLOps architecture stages and parts

Source Code

The CI pipeline starts with the source, such as a model code repository.

The ML pipeline is automatically triggered when a change is pushed to the code repository. Code can be stored on Github, one of the most popular version control systems. With GitHub, you can use branches and pull requests to control what code gets merged where and by whom.

Feature Store

A feature store is a relatively new concept and an optional part of the architecture. For bigger teams training a huge number of models, consider using a feature store. A feature store lets you keep track of the features used to train models. Every model must access the data and do some transformation to turn it into features, which the model then uses for training. These features can be stored, versioned, and organized in a feature store so that models using the same kinds of features can get them directly from the store. This permits the reuse of features across different projects and models.

Feast offers the functionalities for storing and managing features for machine learning models. It supports online and offline features for real time model inference or for model training and batch scoring. To get into more detail about how to create a feature store with Feast, Kedion writes a medium article⁷ exploring this topic further.

ML Pipeline

Kubeflow is a very popular open-source tool for creating ML pipelines (i.e., workflows for building, training, and deploying ML models). This open-source toolkit facilitates the scaling of ML models because it runs on Kubernetes. It handles all the container orchestration and management, allowing data scientists to focus on creating their machine learning workflows. As illustrated in the architecture above, the ML workflow involves defining steps for data processing and manipulation, model training, and validation.

Kubeflow stands on three pillars: scalability, portability, and composability.

It can increase or decrease resources according to the project needs, and your project can run on different types of infrastructure. Composability implies that each component of your project will work even if it is broken down into several independent pieces. As an additional feature, Kubeflow has the possibility of running pipelines simultaneously, running pipelines, and generating several models at once.

The model validation testing stage can be done with **Deep checks**, an open-source tool that utilizes test suits for validating ML models and datasets. It is a flexible option as it integrates very well with Hugging Face, Databricks, and Apache Airflow among other tools. After our model has been validated, we are ready for deployment, and we can move into the CD phase.

⁷ <https://kedion.medium.com/creating-a-feature-store-with-feast-part-1-37c380223e2f>

Model Registry

Figure 8 MLflow and Kubeflow

It's difficult to keep track of how your model was created, where packaged models can be located, and what was done to make them work. A trustworthy model registry including all models' meta-data, such as hyperparameters, metrics, code and dataset versions, and evaluation predictions might be quite useful.

A model registry offers a common location for managing various model artifacts, tracking, and governing models throughout the ML lifecycle. It also provides teams with a way to collaborate at different stages of the life cycle, as it contains several environments, ranging from staging to production to archived.

MLflow is a great fit for this case, as it seamlessly integrates with Kubeflow. It is an easy-to-use open-source platform with a centralized model store that provides APIs for a variety of features. Features like model versioning, production to deployment transitions, annotations, and model lineage. Kubeflow does experiment tracking as well, but it doesn't provide the level of detail as MLflow. Its APIs can be called directly in the pipeline code and all the required model meta-data will be stored in the MLflow server. It is then possible to view all these artifacts via the MLflow user interface.

Model Serving

At this point, the model should be stored in the production environment of a model registry (the MLflow server) and ready to be deployed and served. It quickly becomes apparent that the work is not yet done once the machine learning model is deployed to production. At this point, important questions about the method of shipping the model, accessibility of the model to end-users, optimizing system metrics like latency or uptime, and model scalability should be considered. Teams can try developing their own model deployment platform on Amazon Web Services like EKS or Lambda to solve all these problems, but they can save a ton of time and effort with Cortex.

Cortex is an open-source tool that lets you deploy all types of models allowing your APIs to automatically scale to handle production workloads. It supports multiple frameworks including TensorFlow, pyTorch, and scikit-learn. Cortex can run inference on both CPU

or GPU infrastructure and interestingly updates APIs post-deployment without any downtime.

Model Monitoring

Model monitoring is a continuous process; therefore, it is important to identify the elements for monitoring and create a strategy for handling it. ML systems must be monitored to detect model degradation which can lead to suboptimal performance levels. Operational resources such as GPU usage, and number of API calls should be monitored so the system runs without interruption.

Deep checks is a great tool not only for testing and validating your model, but also for monitoring models after being served. It offers more flexibility as it has an open source and commercial offering, depending on your needs. Other model monitoring tools worth mentioning are **Prometheus** and **Grafana**. Real-time measurements can be tracked by monitoring tools and visualized on a dashboard, gathering both model quality information, such as outlier detection and model drift, as well as operational metrics, such as request rate and latency among others.

MLOps Stage	Candidate Tools	Alternatives
Source Code	Github	Bitbucket
Feature Store	Feast	Hopsworks
ML Pipeline	Kubeflow	Polyaxon
Model Validation Testing/Maintenance	Deepchecks	Etiq AI, Great Expectations
Model Registry	MLFlow	--
Model Serving	Cortex	Seldon Core
Model Monitoring	Deepchecks	Prometheus, Grafana

Table 4 MLOPs architecture tools selection

4 System Requirements

This section describes both the functional and non-functional requirements of AI pipelines.

4.1 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements refer to a set of specifications that outline the tasks that a system must be capable of performing, as well as the way in which those tasks should be carried out. These specifications define the functions, features, and abilities that are essential for a system or software application to satisfy the requirements of its users.

Functional Requirement	Description
Model & Data Versioning	Ability to track and manage different versions of models and datasets.
Pipeline Automation	Creation and management of automated workflows from data ingestion to deployment.
Continuous Testing	Automatically validate the quality and performance of the models
Monitoring & Logging	Track model performance in production and alert for issues.
Feature Management	Efficient storage and access to features for training and inference.
Access Control	Security and permissions for different parts of the process.
Continuous Integration & Deployment	Facilitate regular model deployments with minimal human intervention.
Auditing & Traceability	Record actions and changes to ensure accountability and compliance.
Transparent AI	Incorporation of explainability into the MLOps pipeline, where XAI metrics can be included as a hyperparameter or observation to trigger the re-training of AI models and control their transparency.
Monitoring data	Robust solutions for data lineage, tracking, and monitoring.
Hyperparameters tracking	Tracking hyperparameters, dependencies, and code versions effectively, ensuring reproducibility and transparency in machine learning experiments.

Scalable & Distributed Training	Capabilities to train models on distributed hardware.
Interoperability	Integration with various data and ML tools and platforms.

Table 5 Functional requirements

4.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements are a set of specifications that detail the characteristics, attributes, and qualities of a system or software application, as opposed to its specific functional capabilities. These requirements pertain to the general performance, quality, and usability of the system or software application, rather than its functionalities and features.

The non-functional requirements of the use-case are listed as follows:

Non-Functional Requirement	Description
Scalability	The system's ability to handle increasing workloads.
Availability	The amount of time the system is operational and accessible.
Resilience	Ability to recover quickly from failures.
Latency	Time taken by the system to process a request.
Security	Protection against unauthorized access and threats.
Maintainability	Ease with which the system can be modified.
Portability	Ability to operate in different environments or platforms.
Interoperability	Ability to operate with other systems or components.
Regulatory Compliance	Ensuring the system meets relevant regulations.
Usability	Ease of use and understanding of the system.

Table 6 Non-Functional requirements

5 KPIs & Metrics

There is no one-size-fits-all solution when it comes to MLOps KPIs. The metrics that should be monitored depend on the specific goals and environment. The major KPIs to always keep an eye on when deploying ML software in production include:

KPI	Description
Model optimization iteration time	Duration of a training iteration
Time to deployment	Time from triggering re-training to artifact deployment in production
API calls for AI as a service	Frequency of AI prediction service calls
Model Accuracy	This metric varies depending on the model type and domain. For binary classifiers, an accuracy of 95-99% might be considered excellent, but in complex problems such as fraud detection, 80% might be notable.
Training Time	It depends on the complexity of the model and the size of the data. Ideally, it should be as short as possible (minutes to hours), but deep models might take days.
Prediction Latency	In real-time applications (like transactions or recommendation systems), latency might need to be in milliseconds. For other applications, a few seconds might be acceptable.
Resource Usage	Depends on the infrastructure. Ideally, CPU and memory usage should be below 80% to avoid bottlenecks.
Retraining Frequency	Depends on the domain. Some models need to be retrained daily, others monthly, or even yearly.
Model Drift	Any significant deviation >5% in the feature distribution might require a model review.
Inference Error Rate	The lower, the better. A rate below 1% is often a common target
Recovery Time	In critical systems, it's expected to be in minutes. In less critical systems, it might be hours.

Table 7 KPIs

XAI metrics are used to measure the quality of the original AI model and its explanation. We summarize relevant XAI metrics below:

Metric	Description
Confidence/Faithfulness	The confidence of the explanation relies on the notion of feature relevance. Specifically, observing the effect of muting, i.e., replacing a feature with a baseline value—generally zero—helps to measure the effect on the prediction in both classification and regression tasks.
Log-odds	Similarly, to the confidence, this score is defined as the average difference of the negative logarithmic probabilities on the predicted class before and after masking the top p% features with zero padding. Given the attribution

	<p>scores generated by an explanation algorithm, we select the top p% features based on their attributions and replace them with zero padding.</p>
Comprehensiveness	<p>is the average difference of the change in predicted class probability before and after removing the top p% features. Like Log-odds, this measures the influence of the top-attributed words on the model's prediction.</p>
Sufficiency	<p>is defined as the average difference of the change in predicted class probability before and after keeping only the top p% features. This measures the adequacy of the top p% attributions for the model's prediction. It is defined in a similar fashion as comprehensiveness, except the xi is defined as the samples containing only the top p% features. Lower scores are better.</p>
Interpretability	<p>In XAI surrogate methods, i.e., the schemes that consist of approximating the original model with a low-complexity more interpretable surrogate such as LIME, the fidelity of the surrogate to the original model can be quantified.</p>
Uncertainty	<p>The explanation is certainly linking the input features to the output prediction/decision when high attributions (in absolute value) are more concentrated in some features compared to a less certain uniform distribution.</p>
Robustness/Sensitivity	<p>A crucial property that interpretability methods should satisfy to generate meaningful explanations is that of robustness with respect to local perturbations of the input. This is not the case for popular interpretability methods; even adding minimal white noise to the input introduces visible changes in the explanations.</p>
(in)fidelity	<p>Two metrics can be applied to evaluate fidelity. Firstly, used recall (R) as a measure of fidelity for this method, which is defined as follows,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $R = T \cap E / T$ <p>where the term True Features T represents the relevant features as extracted directly from the white box model and Explanation Features E represents the features characterized as most relevant by the explanation. This measure indicates how well the explanation captures the most relevant features from the predictive model, i.e., as a measure of the completeness of the explanation. Additionally, to understand how well the explanation excludes irrelevant features (soundness of the explanation), precision (P) can be measured,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $P = T \cap E / E$
LIME Explainer R2 Score	<p>Behind the workings of LIME lies the assumption that every complex model is linear on a local scale. LIME tries to fit a simple model around a single observation that will mimic how the global model behaves at that locality. The simple model can then be used to explain the predictions of the more complex model locally. In this respect, R-squared (R2) score is used to measure the performance of the surrogate local model.</p>

Table 8 XAI metrics

6 Conclusion

This document provides a comprehensive analysis of distributed learning (DL) and federated learning (FL), evaluating their strengths and weaknesses in various contexts. It culminates in the proposal of an MLOps architecture, conceptualized as a flexible and scalable Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) framework, specifically tailored to meet the dynamic requirements of 6G networks. This architecture stands out due to its automated machine learning (ML) pipelines, integration of Explainable AI (XAI) metrics for enhanced transparency, and the implementation of Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery (CI/CD) methodologies to facilitate uninterrupted continuous delivery.

A key aspect of this architecture is its emphasis on distributed aspects in MLOps. It is designed to efficiently handle the complexities and challenges associated with distributed data and computing environments, which are characteristic of 6G networks. The architecture's ability to manage real-time data processing, dynamic model deployment on edge devices, and continuous monitoring for model refinement and iterative retraining is particularly noteworthy. These features are crucial for maintaining high-performance ML models in distributed settings, where data sources and computational resources are geographically dispersed and potentially subject to varying constraints and conditions.

The case study on anomaly detection exemplifies the practical application of this architecture. It highlights the system's capability to process data in real-time, deploy models dynamically on edge devices, and conduct vigilant monitoring. This ensures continuous model improvement and retraining, which is vital in distributed environments where data patterns and network conditions can change rapidly. The case study demonstrates the architecture's effectiveness in a real-world scenario, underscoring its suitability for the advanced and distributed nature of 6G network environments.